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Associated project to RESILIENCE

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1. Document overview

1.1. Objectives

WP10 aimed to improve the ecosystem of the European RESILIENCE infrastructure by outlining a shared data model for the integration of religious content resources and by developing a software prototype capable of supporting data publication and greater interaction on the scholar's side in searching and visualising resources. ReTINA had the objective of overcoming a gap in the digital description and accessibility of ancient religious texts from archaeological contexts, promoting a structured approach to their study and dissemination.

The distinctive nature of the field of religious studies — where the cultural meaning of texts and objects must often be linked to specific theological factors — requires the use of descriptors that go beyond the purely linguistic and material level of the sources, since the cultural significance of texts and objects is often deeply intertwined with specific ritual, symbolic, and even magical practices, incorporating immaterial elements such as liturgical functions, therapeutic practices, and transmission contexts (see D10.3). The case study of the Nile Valley and neighbouring geographical contexts represents an emblematic microcosm that can be extended to other cultural areas equally (or more) fragmented.

To this end, ReTINA was tasked with defining which semantic tools could enrich the knowledge and understanding of religious texts and objects, promoting a broader and more interconnected perspective on their meaning and interpretation. This approach also benefited from a series of digital documents to be associated with religious sources — such as photographs, record sheets, 3D digital replicas, and archaeometric analyses — aimed at increasing the depth and accuracy of descriptions while at the same time providing a solid foundation for future digitisation projects.

In summary, WP10 aimed to suggest methodologies that researchers could use to create more interoperable datasets, in order to encourage interdisciplinary studies and ensure that digital resources could more accurately reflect the multifaceted and polysemic nature of religious heritage — without overlooking how beliefs and ritual practices constitute an organising principle of social life.

ReTINA thus strengthens RESILIENCE by providing research enhancement services, particularly dedicated to the digitisation, data integration, and retrieval of information relating to the ancient religious world. The state-of-the-art review specified which metadata are prevalent in the religious studies community, outlining data models that can support the principles and objectives of Open Science and the FAIR recommendations.

1.2. Scope

As demonstrated in the first two deliverables of WP10, D10.1 White Paper: Report on Digital Archives on Ancient Religious Content (DARCAR) (10.5281/zenodo.15025213) and D10.2 Preliminary Data-Model (PRADAM) (10.5281/zenodo.15263295), ReTINA has highlighted

the critical issues connected to the acquisition and processing of religious information from the Nile Valley and beyond. In particular, attention was drawn to the heterogeneity of the sources, the different scholarly traditions and their related classification and taxonomy systems, and the ambiguous nature of the archaeological and epigraphic information pertaining to the world of religion. It was further emphasised that the frequent absence of a find context prevents the correct identification of an object as a tool or component of a religious ceremony. Only through circumstantial interpretation is it possible to recognise the sacred function of a material object, since the other components of a community's religious practices leave no physical traces or have been destroyed by time.

The absence of a reference standard for metadata, or of a more widely adopted data model among researchers, makes the goal of integrating available digital resources for the benefit of the scholarly community even more difficult to achieve. The data structures used by individual institutions do not guarantee the interoperability of resources, and the frequent absence of Persistent Identifiers prevents archives from complying with FAIR principles. Finally — and this is a particularly critical point for the regional context considered by WP10 — there are no archives dedicated exclusively to digital resources of a religious nature.

D10.3 aimed to create an environment that defined guidelines for the digitisation and archiving of a heterogeneous set of sources, taking into account not only material culture but also the difficulties posed by different languages and sometimes unusual writing supports. To manage this informational complexity, ReTINA also intended to propose a prototype capable of supporting scholars in the research and interpretation of a large corpus of ancient objects and texts. In addition to defining procedures for digitising texts and objects and enriching the informational content of sources by creating high-definition photographs and, where possible, 3D replicas, the WP aimed to demonstrate the interconnection between the textual element and the religious component, arising from the very nature of the texts under examination.

One of the main challenges faced by ReTINA concerned the integration of various resources regardless of their chronology, geographical distribution, and cultural characterisation. The survey conducted in D10.1 revealed the absence of a common reference standard for the digitisation of resources, making cross-domain searches across existing archives extremely difficult to carry out. At the same time, the very results of the survey advised against proposing a single data model in D10.2, and instead led to offering scholars an overview of the metadata and ontologies most closely aligned with ITSERR's objectives — although this approach made it harder to achieve more effective semantic interoperability between heterogeneous datasets.

The archives digitised by WP10, made available on the ITSERR MarketPlace, concern datasets developed by UNIOR research groups and relate to archaeological research carried out in different geographical areas and cultures. Unfortunately, it was not possible to extend the digitisation work to include resources belonging to other cultural and/or museum institutions, due to restrictions placed on data access and reuse by those institutions

themselves. Nevertheless, the digitised datasets constitute a fairly significant sample of the issues examined in WP10 and can serve as concrete case studies for the guidelines defined in D10.3 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18508684>).

One of WP10's objectives was to design an interface — easily accessible and user-friendly — capable of supporting researchers not only in the information retrieval phase, but also in the publication of new archives and in the annotation process, that is, the particular stage of research in which a scholar examining a source adds further significant information that must be structured and made available to other researchers.

While D10.3 is dedicated to defining guidelines for the digitisation of resources, this deliverable aims to propose an online system for publishing archives and a system for annotating digital information sources in unstructured language, starting from procedures for handling archaeological, epigraphic, and textual data. It is clear, in light of the objectives of ITSERR and RESILIENCE, that publication must meet the requirements set out by the FAIR recommendations on the one hand, and the research needs of scholars who require the ability to carry out cross-domain searches on the other.

The following sections show how data — manuscripts and material objects — can be processed, described, and annotated using local/national metadata and ultimately published on the Web.

Section 2 illustrates the procedures for the transcription, metadata description, publication, and annotation of a manuscript in the Gə'əz language, held at the Museo di San Domenico in Imola. Section 3 examines the design of a system for the online visualisation of 3D replicas of a number of bowls belonging to a collection of Islamic artefacts housed at the Museo Umberto Scerrato of the University of Naples L'Orientale. The conclusions (Section 4) will highlight how the process of mapping resources onto the Dublin Core schema makes it possible — even if not always entirely satisfactorily — to integrate resources while at the same time exploiting the effectiveness of the OAI-PMH protocol (Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting) for data aggregation. Some aspects examined in WP10 have not always found fully adequate or effective solutions, but the guidelines identified can constitute an important starting point for developing more robust solutions for the integration of heterogeneous sources.

2 Procedures for data processing

2.1 Manuscripts: the transcription

One of the aspects that most interests historians and scholars of linguistics — including those working on languages no longer spoken — is digital transcription: the process by which a manuscript is treated and transformed into a replica that faithfully represents the original document, even using the signs of a different alphabet. Unlike translation, which serves the

cultural understanding of a text, transcription or interlinguistic transposition aims to preserve the register and style of the original. A manuscript digitised in this way is better suited to linguistic analyses based on frequency indices and lemmatisation, as well as to the creation of further tools to improve the text transposition process itself.

The introduction of AI — and above all neural networks that simulate the workings of the human mind — has had a considerable impact on the application of Automatic Text Recognition (ATR) systems. These networks train computers to perform complex functions, including the automatic recognition of textual objects within images. In particular, Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) software, which has rapidly replaced the older Optical Character Recognition (OCR) systems in terms of practical use, employs machine learning techniques that support researchers in improving automatic transcription results, both for handwritten and printed texts. Unlike OCR, HTR can be customised: the more the machine is trained, the better the output it will ultimately generate — exactly as happens with Large Language Models (LLMs).

Collaboration among scholars can undoubtedly help improve the goal of producing consistent systems by introducing large volumes of data, which are particularly useful in the case of manuscripts that, unlike printed texts, exhibit greater variability. For this reason, numerous research projects have been developed over the years, yielding highly encouraging results.

Currently, scholars have two platforms available for automatic transcription: Transkribus (READ Coop) and eScriptorium. These are web-based solutions, widely used in academic and archival research, featuring intuitive graphical interfaces that require no specific technical expertise. The main difference between the two platforms lies in the underlying philosophy of their systems: eScriptorium follows an Open Access approach that allows users to export locally the models they have created. Transkribus, by contrast, has a predominantly commercial objective and permits the sharing of models exclusively within the platform's own cloud space. Since eScriptorium, when installed locally, requires specific technical competencies, Transkribus has had a greater impact on the scholarly community. The growth in its user base has also enabled greater development of its machine learning systems, which has translated into increased platform efficiency. Both systems can train models on individual documents or on large collections of textual resources, although recently general models have also been developed that encompass different scripts, character sets, and so forth.

Similarly to the traditional manual process — which must comply with numerous conversion and validation criteria — HTR must also follow a precise sequence of steps to ensure the robustness and consistency of the transcription process:

1. **Dataset selection:** if necessary, resources may be pre-processed before being imported into the platform in order to improve their legibility, reducing noise caused by elements such as stains or ink bleed-through that can impair the effectiveness of the recognition procedure.
2. **Layout segmentation:** the regions, lines, and text rows of the document are distinguished, differentiating, where necessary, between written sections, images, and annotations.

3. **Model training:** carried out after selecting the ground truth data, consisting of images paired with their transcriptions. Generally, only 10% of the sample is used for subsequent validation.
4. **Model evaluation:** this produces a Character Error Rate (CER), calculated by determining the distance between the correct transcription provided by the user and the transcription generated by the system. This value does not represent an absolute figure, as it is calculated on a test dataset that does not include texts outside the model's training scope.
5. **Fine-tuning:** the model is refined by adding new training data to support the system in areas where recognition shows particular uncertainty.

2.2 Manuscripts in Gə'əz

To illustrate in detail the process of automatic transcription within Transkribus, the recto of the first folio (*folium rectum*) of the Ethiopian manuscript ms. 16429, held at the Museo di San Domenico in Imola, was taken as a case study. This is a religious codex in Gə'əz containing a Ritual for the Baptism (ጥምቀት, *təmqät*) of Christians of the Təwəhədo Church of Ethiopia and Eritrea. The image of the manuscript, acquired at a resolution of 180 DPI, is displayed within the Transkribus interface (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 Transkribus Interface. Loading of the First Page of the Ethiopian Codex from the Museo di San Domenico

Once the upload is complete, the text image is stored in the "Collection" section; at this point it is possible to select the appropriate HTR model for the analysis and transcription of the document. After the recognition process is concluded, the automatically generated transcription will be visible on the right-hand side of the Transkribus screen.

Before examining the transcription, it is worth noting that the *fidäl* — the Ethiopian alpha-syllabary — contains certain characters that differ only slightly from one another, and this similarity makes transcription particularly complex and prone to errors. Indeed, upon analysing the automatic transcription of the first folio of the codex, it was observed that both the penultimate character of the sixth line and that of the seventh were transcribed incorrectly, causing a loss of meaning in the corresponding words. Specifically, instead of ክርስቲና (*krästanna*), meaning "sacrament of baptism", the platform transcribed ክርስቶና (*krästonna*), which has no meaning. Similarly, in the seventh line, instead of መጽሐፈ (*mäṣḥafä*), meaning "book", the platform transcribed መጽሐረ (*mäṣḥarä*). As can be seen, the platform confused the character *tä* (ቲ) in the sixth line with *to* (ቶ), and *fä* (ፈ) in the seventh line with *rä* (ረ). Furthermore, in the eighth line, a confusion arose between *tä* (ቲ) and *tä* (ተ).

Another problematic aspect concerns the poor accuracy in detecting the beginning and end of the ninth line. In the original text, the sentence begins with the character ቲ (*tä*) and ends with the punctuation mark :: (full stop). In the transcription, these elements are absent.

These shortcomings highlight the current limitations of the platform for texts written in *fidäl*. However, these errors were corrected manually using the interactive revision tools offered by the platform itself, which allowed direct intervention on the transcribed text. Despite the imperfections that emerged, Transkribus nonetheless demonstrated a high overall level of accuracy in the transcription of the manuscript.

Figure 2 Transkribus Interface. Automatic Transcription with Some Errors.

Figure 3 Transkribus Interface. Manually Corrected Transcription of the Same Manuscript

2.3 Manuscripts: the metadata

Once the digital transcription of the Ethiopian manuscript was obtained via Transkribus, the encoding process was carried out following the guidelines of the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI), an international standard based on XML that enables digital texts to be described in a structured and interoperable manner. TEI is distinguished by its flexibility and adaptability, offering a descriptive framework capable of supporting the encoding of texts of any genre, language, and historical period. This versatility is made possible by a methodological approach grounded in two principles that appear contradictory but are in fact complementary: on the one hand, it is assumed that all texts are similar, in that they share common structures — such as the presence of titles, paragraphs, and so forth; on the other hand, it is recognised that every text is unique, as it carries specific and unrepeatable characteristics.

Every document encoded in XML/TEI is organised according to a hierarchy that distinguishes the descriptive component (metadata) from the textual one. The two main macro-sections are:

<teiHeader>: the document "header", which contains information such as the title of the work, the author, the date, the place of preservation, the licence, etc.

```
<teiHeader>
  <fileDesc>
    <titleStmt>
      <title>
        <!-- title of the resource -->
      </title>
    </titleStmt>
    <publicationStmt>
      <p>
        <!-- Information about distribution of the resource -->
      </p>
    </publicationStmt>
    <sourceDesc>
      <p>
        <!-- Information about source from which the resource derives -->
      </p>
    </sourceDesc>
  </fileDesc>
</teiHeader>
```

Figure 4 <https://tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/it/html/examples-teiHeader.html>

<text>: the section containing the text, including the preliminary and final parts. The text may be enriched with annotations, translations, and commentary.

```
<text>
  <body>
    <p>This is about the shortest TEI document imaginable.</p>
  </body>
</text>
</TEI>
```

Figure 5 <https://tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/it/html/examples-teiHeader.html>

For the encoding of the texts, Oxygen XML Editor (version 27.0) was used — one of the most widely adopted and comprehensive programs for creating, editing, and validating XML/TEI documents. The software enables automatic checking of structure and syntax, ensuring adherence to the TEI schema through real-time validation, thereby reducing encoding errors.

The Ethiopian manuscript subject to encoding (ID: 16419) is a single folio written in red ink, containing 13 lines of text in the Gə'əz language. The image used for transcription was acquired at a resolution of 180 DPI. The text concerns a prayer of a magico-religious nature directed against malevolent forces, in particular against entities such as the Buda, Zar, Wəlaḡ, and Qumäñña. The content is highly repetitive, suggesting an apotropaic and performative function, likely intended for the protection of a single individual, as indicated by the final mention of the feminine name 'Əḥtä Maryam Asägädäč (እኅተ : ማርያም : አሰገደች).

Upon completing the encoding of ms. 16419 according to TEI guidelines and saving the file with the .xml extension, the "Configure Transformation Scenario(s)" function was tested. This function employs TEI P5 XHTML to generate a browser-viewable output that is fully compatible with TEI, preserving its structure and semantic richness. This transformer is part

of a broader set of conversion tools, which also includes options for generating output in PDF, EPUB, ODT, and DOCX formats.

During the encoding process, the title of the manuscript (ms. 16419) was identified within the text itself, since in Ethiopian manuscripts written in Gə‘əz the title of a work is generally not given in an explicit paratextual position but must be identified within the content. The title thus identified was marked using the element `<title type="full" xml:lang="gez">`, which contains the original form in fidäl followed by its transliteration into Latin characters, in accordance with the conventions adopted by the *Encyclopaedia Aethiopica* (EAe). An English translation of the title was also provided, encoded separately using the attribute `xml:lang="en"` within a further `<title>` element.

Since, in the XHTML transformation generated via the TEI P5 XHTML engine, only a portion of the information contained in the `<teiHeader>` is visible in the browser — specifically the content of the `<title>` element within `<titleStmt>` — it was deemed appropriate to replicate the most relevant descriptive metadata within the `<text>` section, in order to make them accessible to the user.

The replicated metadata includes: the manuscript identification number (ID), dating, geographical provenance, writing material, physical dimensions of the support, manuscript language, holding institution, and a brief description of the content. The elements used to convey these textual metadata include, for example:

`<hi rend="bold">` to indicate titles and subtitles that structure the informational sections

`<placeName>`, `<settlement>`, `<country>` for the geolocation of the manuscript

`<lang>` to indicate the language of the text (Gə‘əz), translations, or notes in English

Regarding the structure of the content, the body of the text is organised into distinct semantic blocks by means of the `<div>` element, which serves as a structural container. Each `<div>` element is identified via the `@type` attribute, which allows the textual segments to be classified according to their content or function:

`<div type="1">` contains descriptive and contextual information about the manuscript;

`<div type="2">` houses the actual transcription of the text.

The manuscript text was transcribed faithfully, respecting the original order and line segmentation. Line breaks were marked using the `<lb/>` element, in order to maintain legibility and visual correspondence with the physical support, in which the lines are clearly delimited and graphically distinct.

Particular attention was paid to semantic marking, through the use of the <hi> element, employed to highlight sacred formulae, invocations, and relevant lexical units such as references to the "evil eye", ailments, and spiritual entities. Explanatory notes, rendered via <note place="end" xml:lang="eng">, provide translations or English-language explanations for passages deemed significant. Examples include the opening Trinitarian formula: "በሰሙ : ኣብ : ወወልድ : ወመንፈስ : ቅዱስ : ፩ አምላክ" (*In the name of the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit, one God*), or expressions such as "ዓይነ : ጥላ" (*evil eye*) and "ዓይነ : ወርቅ" (*jaundice*). The notes are numbered progressively via the @n attribute (n="1", n="2", etc.) and placed as footnotes in the visual rendering. Textual passages that are obscure or difficult to read are marked with <unclear>.

The representation of special characters — such as the glottal stop (‘) or the mid-central vowel (ə), commonly known as schwa — was achieved through the use of Unicode numerical entities expressed in XML. This choice was necessary because such characters are not always accepted or correctly handled by XML parsers, resulting in display issues. For example, in the transliteration of the word Gə‘əz, the numerical entities ə were used to represent the vowel ə and ʿ for the glottal stop ‘, yielding the encoding <lang>Gəʿəz</lang>. The use of numerical entities ensures the correct graphic and phonetic rendering of the text, preserving its integrity even on platforms that do not fully support these characters.

The integration of automatic text recognition and XML/TEI encoding highlights the potential of digital technologies applied to manuscript heritage, while at the same time underscoring the necessity of human intervention during the revision phase — especially for texts written in complex writing systems such as Gə‘əz.

The following figure illustrates the output of ms. 16419, generated using Oxygen XML Editor with the TEI P5 XHTML transformer.

in D10.1 and D10.2, the absence of an internationally recognised standard for the metadata description of digital resources led to the adoption of a basic schema such as Dublin Core to support the integration of archives.

The transition from TEI to Dublin Core — technically defined as *mapping* — is based on the creation of a conceptual correspondence between two sets of elements that identify a structured relationship between a source schema and a target one. In this way, a description is obtained that is compatible with the schema chosen for the final destination of the object.

Since TEI is a complex standard for encoding texts in XML, modelling in detail the internal structure of a document (chapters, paragraphs, notes, etc.), it is difficult to design a mapping onto Dublin Core, which instead represents a schema that catalogues resources in a synthetic and essential manner. The two schemas can be considered complementary rather than fully alternative, though not without a significant loss of semantic content — offset, however, by the gain in interoperability. Dublin Core is, in fact, the preferred metadata schema for the OAI-PMH protocol, which guarantees integration between different archives.

Although Dublin Core acts as a lingua franca for metadata exchange, no official mapping proposal from TEI exists in the literature. Many repositories containing TEI data expose metadata in Dublin Core via OAI-PMH. The limitations of mapping lie not only in the information lost in the transition between different structures, but also in the fact that a single TEI element may map onto multiple Dublin Core fields — and above all because the resulting schema lacks a hierarchical structure.

The following table presents a proposal for a formal mapping between the two formats.

Table 1 Description of the mapping of the MS16149 on DCTerms

TEI	Qualificatore	DCTERMS	Note
author	author	dcterms:creator	Author of the work
title	none	dcterms:title	Title
corpus	none	dcterms:type	DCMI Vocabulary ("Text")
date	issued	dcterms:issued	Digital publication date
parametro	uri	dcterms:identifier	Identifier
responsabile	none	dcterms:contributor	Editorial responsibilities
project desk	none	dcterms:provenance	Project information
editor	nome	dcterms:contributor	Role: editor
contributor	-	dcterms:contributor	Contributors
language	iso	dcterms:language	ISO 639-2 code
publisher	none	dcterms:publisher	Publishing institution
sourceDesc	uri	dcterms:source	Source URL

TEI	Qualificatore	DCTERMS	Note
keywords	none	dcterms:subject	Subjects/Keywords
availability	none	dcterms:rights	Rights
availability	uri	dcterms:license	Licence URL
availability	label	dcterms:accessRights	Access type

With few exceptions (responsible party, editor, contributors, project information, source URL), the mapping does not show any particular weaknesses.

In detail, it is clear that TEI maintains a precise editorial structure (author, editor, respStmt, projectDesc, sourceDesc, availability, etc.), whereas Dublin Core uses more generic and descriptive elements (creator, contributor, description, rights, etc.). As a result, multiple TEI fields end up within the same Dublin Core element, owing to the latter's lower granularity. In particular, TEI distinguishes editorial roles, whereas Dublin Core flattens them into creator or contributor. TEI features complex elements, in contrast to Dublin Core, which maintains atomic fields. For example:

- <sourceDesc> in TEI can contain complex structures → in DC it becomes a simple dcterms:source
- <availability> in TEI can contain text, URIs, and labels → in DC it is split into:
 - dcterms:rights
 - dcterms:license
 - dcterms:accessRights

TEI uses flexible internal vocabularies; Dublin Core uses standardised vocabularies to ensure interoperability. TEI is content-oriented, while Dublin Core is metadata-oriented. In the table, TEI has elements such as <keywords>, <projectDesc>, and <respStmt> that describe the editorial process; DC maps these onto very generic values such as dcterms:subject or dcterms:description. In summary, TEI is highly detailed, structured, and text-oriented, whereas Dublin Core is simple, flat, and oriented towards the description of the resource. Consequently, many TEI elements must be simplified or merged for mapping onto Dublin Core.

Ms. 16419 is thus converted as follows:

<dcterms:description>The manuscript, written in red ink and consisting of 13 lines, was donated to the Museo di San Domenico by General Carlo Manara in 1944. </dcterms:description>

</rdf:Description>

</rdf:RDF>

The TEI/DC conversion process retains cases of ambiguity that are not always mappable without human intervention. A greater availability of cases could provide a critical assessment of the impact of mapping and of the alignment of different metadata schemas, languages, and formats. Nevertheless, the choice of Dublin Core as a lingua franca appears at this stage to be an unavoidable step, though the problem of semantic loss remains open. Perhaps an application profile of DC could represent a more viable solution, as could the experimentation with other schemas (EDM, CIDOC-CRM, etc.) — which might, however, raise further critical issues.

2.5 Manuscripts: the online publication

The workflow illustrated in the following figure schematically outlines the steps that prepare the sources for a Web-based visualisation of the manuscript, which thereby becomes consultable by users and, where applicable, integrable with other datasets.

After transcribing the manuscript using the Transkribus platform, tagging it manually according to the TEI schema, and finally mapping it onto Dublin Core via a stylesheet, the processed data can be displayed on a Web page. In order to align the resources with the FAIR recommendations, it is necessary to implement an accessible repository that provides each resource with a Persistent Identifier.

The following figure shows the three aligned and viewable resources; it is clear that TEI tagging is far more complex than that generated in Dublin Core after transforming the manuscript transcription.

To create a DH-GRADE (Digital Humanities-grade) architecture — capable of meeting the quality standards of the Digital Humanities — beyond the use of standardised formats such as TEI-XML and Dublin Core, it is necessary to implement an advanced image visualisation function. The choice of the open IIIF standard fits perfectly into this framework, contributing to the definition of an ideal digital ecosystem for linking manuscript images to transcriptions encoded in TEI. Furthermore, the possibility of selecting the XSLT on the user side makes the procedure more flexible and adaptable to the needs of the scholar, who can experiment with their own specific TEI2DC mapping. The Dublin Core file thus generated can be downloaded in RDF format.

In order to enhance the semantic value of the data — and consequently its connectivity with other data — an additional function was added that replaces the simple tags of textual strings with tags carrying attributes (rdf:resource), so as to correctly express URIs drawn from controlled vocabularies and international standards such as ISO 639-2 (languages), GeoNames (places), VIAF/ORCID (names), LibraryOfCongress (roles), and Wikidata (museums, cultural institutions, etc.). The "enrich with URIs" button generates a new Dublin Core file in which the unique identifiers (Linked Data) are clickable and open in a new page.

The final architecture was designed as the outcome of a semantic and technological layering that separates presentation data (the image) from structured data (TEI) and interoperable metadata (Dublin Core), while promoting the use of Linked Open Data.

Figure 9 Web application showing the visualisation of the manuscript, the TEI encoding and DC transformation

The HTML file, created to test the prototype, is a client-side Single Page Application whose main function is the synchronised visualisation of digital manuscripts, mediating between different data encoding standards. Technically, it is not a simple list of metadata, but a knowledge graph expressed in triples.

Associated project to RESILIENCE

🔗 URIs and Linked Data added!

XSLT Transformation File

Load XSLT

🔗 Generate DC (RDF/XML)

🔗 Enrich with URIs

📄 Download DC RDF/XML

```

<class="xml-tag">rdf:RDF
xmlns:rdf="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-
ns#" xmlns:tei="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0"
xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/"
xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/"
xmlns:dctype="http://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/">
  <class="xml-tag">rdf:Description
rdf:about="https://doi.org/10.xxxx/ms_16419">
    <class="xml-tag">dcterms:type
rdf:resource="http://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/Text"/>
    <class="xml-tag">dcterms:title
xml:lang="gez">ጸሎት በእግዓዥ ስፍራ ላይ ለጸሎት ሰጪ ግለሰብ ለጸሎት ሰጪ ግለሰብ (፻፲፬ ዓ.ም. ለጸሎት ሰጪ ግለሰብ)
wäZar Wēlaḅ wäQumäñña</class="xml-
tag">dcterms:title>
    <class="xml-tag">dcterms:title
xml:lang="en">Prayer against the trap of the spirits
of enchantment: Buda, Zar, Wēlaḅ, and
Qumäñña</class="xml-tag">dcterms:title>
    <class="xml-tag">dcterms:language
rdf:resource="http://id.loc.gov/vocabulary/iso639-
2/gez"/>
    <class="xml-tag">dcterms:language
rdf:resource="http://id.loc.gov/vocabulary/iso639-
2/en"/>
    <class="xml-tag">dcterms:publisher
rdf:resource="http://viaf.org/viaf/135934335"/>
    <class="xml-tag">dcterms:description>The
manuscript, written in red ink and consisting of 13
lines, was donated to the Museo di San Domenico by
General Carlo Manara in 1944.</class="xml-
tag">dcterms:description>
    <class="xml-tag">dcterms:relation
rdf:resource="file://ms. 16419.jpg"/>
    <class="xml-tag">dcterms:provenance
rdf:resource="https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q27992740

```

Figure 10 Web application showing the DC transformation and URI enrichments

The technological core of the page is managed by Vanilla JavaScript, which operates entirely within the user's browser without the need for a backend server. This architecture ensures that the final output is not merely a web page displaying data for a user to view, but a scientific digital object that complies with the FAIR principles. The underlying idea of the prototype assumes the use of Dublin Core — even in its semantically enriched form — to support data aggregation and retrieval across different repositories, while once the desired

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page is reached, the researcher can consult the original manuscript image and the more detailed TEI mapping.

2.5 Manuscript: the online annotation

One of the objectives of D10.4 also consisted in the design of a prototype for the annotation of texts, manuscripts, and objects; the notes associated with digital resources were to be subsequently displayed and archived using a standard, so as to be easily searchable and linkable to the original source.

The annotation process connects information to visual regions (rectangles, polygons, points, etc.) or to the image as a whole. The aim is to add further contextual data or general knowledge to a digital source in order to enrich its informational content and clarify its meaning and any relationships with other digital objects. Raw data can thus be transformed into structured resources, enabling exchange between different systems and — above all — supporting concept-based searches.

Annotation is carried out by tagging documents, which thereby become easier to find, interpret, and reuse, provided a formal language comprehensible to both humans and machines is employed. Furthermore, the process of adding notes — whether in standardised form or not — fosters collaboration among different researchers, each of whom can associate information specific to their own field of expertise. The level of detail and granularity of a note clearly depends on the choices of the researcher annotating the source and cannot be rigidly circumscribed.

By way of example only, the following tagging needs can be identified:

- The data entered are incorrect and need to be clarified (context, chronology, provenance, etc.);
- Some data are absent from the description of the object or its metadata, as they relate to specific investigations or analyses (such as chemical-physical or petrographic examinations, conservation status, etc.) not previously carried out;
- The annotated object has comparanda — that is, stylistic, production, or provenance relationships — with other material sources found at different sites or at the same place of discovery.

The first type of annotation is *Embedded*, meaning it is inserted within the selected document itself; the other two are defined as *Attached*. However, while the first two link directly to the object under examination — whose cataloguing and classification are improved by correcting, modifying, or adding notes — the third tagging case identifies rather a cultural or chronological relationship that the user establishes with other objects on the basis of their

own knowledge. In any case, all three scenarios expand the quality of the information, whose meaning is undoubtedly richer and more scientifically relevant.

At a practical level, a distinction is made between annotations entered in natural language and unconnected to any schema, those that use standard metadata also interpretable by machines, and finally those that employ a formal knowledge representation language with terminology referring to shared ontological schemas.

Numerous tools have been developed to support the annotation process for digital resources. These programmes are often designed to automate the tagging phase rather than to serve as working instruments for researchers. The primary requirement is the design of formal solutions and procedures capable of capturing the meaning of data while reducing manual data encoding tasks. The tools fall into three categories:

- ontology-based, ideal for the Semantic Web and formal knowledge representation;
- useful for training NLP models;
- developed to automate the semantic extraction of tags.

Unlike what has been implemented and made available thus far, the annotation prototype envisaged by D10.4 is conceived as a genuine scientific tool that researchers consulting the ITSERR or RESILIENCE database can use to comment on the source they are examining, proposing corrections, modifications, or additions to the original content. It is not a tool designed to support the construction of a database associated with a standard metadata system, but a procedure that a scholar can use in their research activity to comment on a digital resource without necessarily resorting to a structured annotation code or a complex data schema. Such a procedure — which favours the use of natural language — helps improve collaboration among users and consolidate the scholarly community.

To support researchers in the annotation process, a prototype was designed that allows the loading of a local image or an IIIF URL. The displayed image can be selected in full or in part using a rectangle, a point, a freehand tool, or similar. The annotation tools allow any comment to be written in natural language. The annotations are subsequently listed and can be selected, deleted, and finally exported to a JSON-LD file, after indicating the author of the note and their institutional affiliation — information essential for subsequent mapping onto Dublin Core. The output contains the ID corresponding to the name of the annotated file including its extension, and the date on which the comment was entered.

In this case too, the prototype is a fully client-side single-page web application that requires no backend, uses no database, runs entirely in the browser, and is composed of HTML, CSS, and JavaScript in a single file. The application logic is based on Vanilla JavaScript, while the technical core of the file is the external OpenSeadragon library, used as a DeepZoom image viewer.

The code implements two international standards to ensure data interoperability:

- **W3C Web Annotation Data Model:** the generated JSON file is not a simple list but follows the AnnotationPage structure. Each annotation has a target (the image) and a selector (the specific area).
- **Dublin Core (DC):** the author and date metadata are mapped using the Dublin Core vocabulary (dc:creator, dc:date), the standard in the field of digital cultural heritage.

Figure 11 Web application showing the Image Annotation interface

In order to describe annotations in an interoperable, formal, and machine-readable manner, it was decided to add an export option also in RDF/XML format, based on the OA (Open Annotation) schema — or W3C Web Annotation Data Model. The OA represents annotations as structured objects that link a content (body) to a resource or part of it (target). The annotation action (oa:Annotation) contains an author (dc:creator), a date, a body (oa:hasBody), and a target (oa:hasTarget). The body can be a text, a tag, a link, or an external resource. The target is the selected portion of the object under examination. With oa:Selector, one defines exactly which part of the image has been annotated. In this way, the annotation activity can be unified by connecting the different observed portions.

The resulting file — encoded according to a specific standard for the creation of notes and comments — nonetheless contains a significant descriptive section written in natural language, so as to simplify the researcher's work. The risk inherent in such an approach, which favours the use of unstructured descriptions, is that of weakening the efficient querying of notes, particularly within a system whose aim is to aggregate resources.

2.6 Manuscripts: the use of ER and NER algorithms for the automatic classification

In order to understand and make use of information that is often not organised in a standardised format, WP10 experimented with the use of AI and supervised knowledge models for the automatic extraction of elements such as categories, names, and places. By drawing on data analysis, it is possible to produce semantic labelling of data, aggregation of content, and subsequent integration with other resources, making them available for research.

Entity Extraction and Named Entity Recognition (NER) are two important natural language processing techniques used to identify, extract, and classify key information (names, organisations, places, dates, etc.) in unstructured documents. The entity extraction process highlights specific information carrying a particular meaning within a text. NER identifies specific words or phrases and classifies them according to entity type; Entity Extraction then retrieves further information specific to that precise entity, such as attributes from the entity itself. Both techniques are based on the tokenisation or segmentation of the sentences and words of a text, which is thus broken down, enabling the classification of entities alone while excluding other syntactic parts of speech (verbs, articles, prepositions, etc.). Both methods are used to recognise names of people, organisations, places, and dates, as well as to extract additional information linked to the highlighted concepts, connecting to external databases of a generalist nature (DBpedia, Wikipedia) or specialised ones (GeoNames, Getty AAT, VIAF, ROR, etc.).

The system compares the input text against a dictionary or Knowledge Base containing predefined entities; if a word matches an entry in the dictionary, it is classified as an entity. Although these methods are fast and effective for recognising already known entities, they are unable to identify new concepts or linguistic variants not present in the dictionaries. By drawing on semantic technologies such as the Knowledge Graph — which contribute to the identification of context — a more accurate labelling can be produced, clarifying the meaning of words. Such an approach allows specific terms to be mapped by linking them to the nodes of ontology, with the aim of improving the accuracy and effectiveness of entity recognition and classification.

To verify the functioning and applicability of these techniques to the analysis of manuscript content, a Python script was designed that manages specific modules for assisted semantic annotation. The system aims at the extraction, disambiguation, and semantic annotation of named entities in descriptive texts of manuscripts, with particular attention to specialised contexts not adequately covered by generalist NER models, such as that of Ethiopian manuscripts.

ITSERR Semantic Annotator is a desktop application for the semantic annotation of XML documents, oriented towards the automatic identification of entities and their enrichment through Linked Open Data resources. Its primary objective is to support digital humanities workflows, cultural archives, and research contexts, offering an interactive tool that integrates linguistic analysis, linking to heterogeneous knowledge bases, and advanced visualisation of results. The application aims in particular to move beyond the approach based on a single endpoint (such as DBpedia), by introducing a parallel and intelligent search strategy that gives priority to specialised services according to the semantic type of the entity.

From an architectural standpoint, the application is organised into three levels: linguistic analysis logic, semantic enrichment services, and graphical interface. The pipeline is encapsulated in an external module that receives the XML tree, the language, and a confidence threshold as input, and returns a set of entities annotated with category and probability. This design keeps the linguistic analysis decoupled from the interface and Linked Data services, facilitating the replaceability of the NER engine.

The innovative core of the application is represented by the "intelligent search" service, responsible for semantic enrichment. This component implements a model of parallel querying across numerous heterogeneous knowledge bases, including GeoNames, Pleiades, VIAF, GND, ROR, Wikidata, Europeana, and others. The services are classified according to priority and support semantic categories, enabling the system to dynamically select the most appropriate resources for each entity. Searches are executed in parallel, significantly reducing response times and improving informational coverage. Results are normalised, deduplicated, and ranked, and a "best match" is identified on the basis of heuristic rules dependent on the entity category.

The data representation layer is enriched with URI lists for each service, coverage measures, and an implicit confidence score. This data structure acts as a bridge between the backend logic and the visualisation layer, allowing uniform access to results.

The typical operational workflow involves loading an XML document, analysing it through the NER pipeline, and then proceeding to the semantic enrichment phase. The user can choose between different search modes, including an "intelligent" search that prioritises specialised services and a more extensive mode that queries all enabled resources. Results

are presented in interactive textual form, with clickable links to external resources, and can be exported in RDF or HTML format for subsequent use in publication or interoperability contexts.

Among the application's main strengths is its high degree of integration with Linked Open Data resources, which produces a richer and more accurate output compared to solutions based on a single endpoint. The parallel approach and the priority assigned to specialised services improve both performance and result quality. A further advantage lies in the flexibility of the interface, which allows the user to configure services, search parameters, and confidence thresholds without modifying the underlying code.

The application does, however, present some structural limitations that will need to be addressed in future development. Reliance on numerous external APIs introduces a significant dependency on the availability and stability of remote services, as well as on the rate limits and demo keys used. The heuristics for "best match" selection, while effective in many cases, remain static rules and do not learn from use or from the specific context of the document. Furthermore, the application is oriented towards desktop and local use, which may limit its scalability in collaborative or high-volume data contexts.

A natural evolution of the application will need to be based on the introduction of disambiguation models grounded in machine learning, capable of exploiting textual context and knowledge graphs to automatically select the best URI from among the candidates. A second area for improvement concerns the persistence and reusability of results — for example, through integration with a local or remote triple store that would allow the produced annotations to be stored and queried. Further developments could include the integration of standards such as Web Annotation or IIF for linking to digital resources, and mechanisms for the quantitative assessment of annotation quality, useful in comparative research contexts.

Figure 12 Interface of the Annotation NER application

The final data can be saved and exported in RDF/XML or HTML format for a quick report of the annotations and identified Linked Data.

The results obtained through the implementation and testing of ITSERR Semantic Annotator are encouraging and point the challenge towards the training of domain-specific language models capable of understanding the meaning of terms within a precise context of use. At present, although it is possible to automatically identify entities, the lack of domain-specific databases hampers unambiguous semantic annotation. The availability of specialised archives could also support the metadata description phase of resources starting from TEI and its migration to DC, as well as the conversion of values into URIs in accordance with the principles of Linked Open Data and FAIR data.

Report NER Risultati

- **Prayer**
<http://dbpedia.org/resource/Prayer>
<http://dbpedia.org/page/Prayer>
<https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Prayer>
<https://www.google.com/search?q=Prayer&hl=it>
- **trap**
<https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/trap>
<https://www.google.com/search?q=trap&hl=it>
- **enchantment**
<https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/enchantment>
<https://www.google.com/search?q=enchantment&hl=it>
- **Zar**
<http://dbpedia.org/resource/Zar>
<http://dbpedia.org/page/Zar>
<https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Zar>
<https://www.google.com/search?q=Zar&hl=it>
- **Naples**
<http://dbpedia.org/resource/Naples>
<http://dbpedia.org/page/Naples>
<https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Naples>
<https://www.google.com/search?q=Naples&hl=it>
- **Naples**
<http://dbpedia.org/resource/Naples>
<http://dbpedia.org/page/Naples>
<https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Naples>
<https://www.google.com/search?q=Naples&hl=it>
- **San Domenico**
http://dbpedia.org/resource/San_Domenico
http://dbpedia.org/page/San_Domenico
https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/San_Domenico
<https://www.google.com/search?q=San%20Domenico&hl=it>

Figure 13 List of the results after NER application

3. 3D V.I.S.O.R. (Virtual Interface for Scientific Object Reconstruction)

3.1. Introduction to the system workflow

A further objective of WP10 was the implementation of a prototype capable of displaying and querying the textual and epigraphic objects uploaded. The 3D V.I.S.O.R. workflow was conceived to address the need to centralise, enrich, and visualise archaeological and textual data from heterogeneous contexts. The architecture is based on a paradigm of separation between the backend (managed via Django and Django REST Framework) and the frontend

(React), ensuring that every phase of the workflow — from ingestion to access — is scalable and compliant with FAIR principles.

The architecture of the portal does not merely represent a technical choice, but reflects a scientific research methodology applied to digital data. In order to broaden the concept of the system workflow, it is necessary to analyse how the separation between backend and frontend becomes the driving force behind a more fluid and secure management of archaeological data.

The decision to separate the Backend from the Frontend responds to the need to manage different data lifecycle requirements. While the backend handles long-term persistence, security, and the integrity of archaeological data, the frontend evolves rapidly to offer increasingly high-performing visualisation tools (such as 3D rendering). This "decoupling" ensures that updates to visualisation tools never compromise the certified database.

In the 3D V.I.S.O.R. workflow, Django does not merely function as a server, but as a guarantor of data quality through:

- **Centralisation:** all data coming from external repositories (such as cataloguing metadata) or from local uploads (3D models, photographs) converge at a single point of control.
- **Standardisation via DRF:** Django REST Framework transforms all information into a standard format (JSON), making the data "interoperable" by definition. This means that the data uploaded and organised by the backend could, in the future, be queried by other research infrastructures without structural modifications.

If the backend is the archive, the frontend is the scholar's workbench, enabling:

- **Scalable access:** React allows the complexity of 3D models and real-time annotations to be handled without reloading the page, transforming the consultation of an artefact into an exploratory experience.
- **Modularity:** component-based architecture allows new tools to be added (such as a new type of virtual ruler or a texture analysis filter) in an isolated manner, without rewriting the entire interface.

The workflow is designed to respect the FAIR principles:

- **Findable:** automatic indexing of metadata in the backend ensures that every artefact is traceable.
- **Accessible:** the DRF APIs ensure that data is always available via standard web protocols.
- **Interoperable:** the separation between data and presentation allows the artefacts held in the backend to "communicate" with other systems.

- **Reusable:** the documentation of the code on GitHub and the clarity of the architecture ensure that the work carried out today can serve as the foundation for future research projects.

In summary, V.I.S.O.R. is not a simple file upload and display pathway, but a transformation infrastructure that elevates the raw file (the 3D model or photograph) into an enriched "digital object" ready for scientific collaboration.

3.2. Data Ingestion and Retrieval from External Repositories

A further objective of WP10 was the implementation of a prototype capable of displaying and querying the textual and epigraphic objects uploaded. The 3D V.I.S.O.R. workflow was conceived to address the need to centralise, enrich, and visualise archaeological and textual data from heterogeneous contexts. The architecture is based on a paradigm of separation between the backend (managed via Django and Django REST Framework) and the frontend (React), ensuring that every phase of the workflow — from ingestion to access — is scalable and compliant with FAIR principles.

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In summary, V.I.S.O.R. is not a simple file upload and display pathway, but a transformation infrastructure that elevates the raw file (the 3D model or photograph) into an enriched "digital object" ready for scientific collaboration.

Figure 14 Illustration of the V.I.S.O.R. portal architecture, highlighting the crucial role of the Django REST Framework backend, which acts as a true "director" for the management and visualisation of data relating to both artefacts and three-dimensional models.

Figure 17 The React interface of V.I.S.O.R. for uploading compressed folders.

- ZIP file: `modelli_3d/[model-name]/[file]`. This structure is not arbitrary, but allows the backend to logically isolate each model, avoiding conflicts between files that might share similar names (such as the classic `texture.jpg` or `material.mtl`) yet belong to different artefacts.
- **Slug Generation and Identification:** during the parsing phase, the backend transforms the folder name into a "slug" (a normalised string, free of spaces or special characters). This slug is used to query the database:
 - *Existing Match:* if the slug corresponds to a record already created (perhaps previously imported from the external repository), the system "attaches" the new 3D files to the existing entry.
 - *Auto-Generation:* if no record exists, the system can be configured to create a new instance of `MyModel`, using the slug as a temporary identifier to be validated at a later stage.
- **The Cross-Reference with the Proxy Layer:** the true added value emerges when the system cross-references the data from the ZIP file with those coming from the external repository via the Django proxy. If a folder is named using the official identification code of the artefact (e.g. `MO1138`), the system bypasses any ambiguity, performing an automatic association between the 3D geometry and the complete R.A. record of the artefact.

This workflow eliminates at the root the risk of manual transcription errors (typos) and ensures that the data displayed in the frontend is always scientifically anchored to the correct record held in the backend, guaranteeing a level of data integrity that is fundamental for scientific publications and archaeological research.

Figure 18 The model acquisition process in Bulk Upload mode

Figure 19 Successful upload: the frontend has communicated correctly with the backend, and the files contained in the compressed archive have not only been uploaded, but have also been associated with an existing artefact in the database

```

{
  "id": 1,
  "name": "Modello Prova",
  "description": "Bulk upload da ZIP: Prova",
  "obj_file": "http://127.0.0.1:8000/media/modelli_3d/modello-prova/M01139.obj",
  "mtl_file": "http://127.0.0.1:8000/media/modelli_3d/modello-prova/M01139.mtl",
  "textures": [
    {
      "id": 54,
      "url": "http://127.0.0.1:8000/media/modelli_3d/modello-prova/M01139.png",
      "description": null
    },
    {
      "id": 55,
      "url": "http://127.0.0.1:8000/media/modelli_3d/modello-prova/M01138.jpg",
      "description": null
    }
  ],
  "created_at": "2026-01-29T22:36:29.820429Z",
  "annotazioni": []
},

```

Figure 20 The backend has correctly "hosted" the files relating to the three-dimensional models, and through a matching process that takes place simultaneously with the acquisition, they are incorporated into the one-to-one relationships of the artefacts, which become the "primary key".

3.3 Technical and Procedural Issues in Model Management

The transition from a physical artefact to a scientifically valid digital entity is not a process without obstacles. During the development of the 3D VIEWER portal, the management of 3D assets brought to light structural issues that required the implementation of specific algorithmic solutions.

One of the most recurring problems concerns the misalignment of paths in MTL files. During export from modelling software (such as Blender or 3ds Max), MTL files often retain absolute references to the local file paths on the modeller's computer (e.g. C:\Users\Desktop\Texture\marble.jpg).

To address this issue, the workflow includes an automatic "sanitisation" phase. The server analyses the MTL file upon upload, identifies the path strings, and rewrites them dynamically to point correctly to Django's media server structure. This ensures that the model is rendered correctly in the browser without any "missing" textures, regardless of the original file configuration.

Scientific fidelity requires high-resolution models, which can however prove prohibitive for smooth web navigation over inadequate network connections. To overcome these drawbacks, the following solutions were adopted:

- **Lazy Loading and Progressive Visualisation:** in React, a differentiated loading management system was implemented. Using the Suspense library and lazy loading

logic, the portal first displays the interface and textual metadata (retrieved instantaneously from the proxy layer), while the 3D model is loaded in the background.

- **User Experience (UX):** this approach avoids browser blocking, allowing the researcher to consult the R.A. record while the Three.js rendering engine initialises the 3D scene.

The bulk upload pipeline described earlier — which involves a ZIP file containing n subfolders named with the unique artefact codes — is not merely an operational recommendation, but a system requirement. In a project of international scope such as ITSERR, data heterogeneity represents the greatest risk. The adoption of a naming standard based on artefact codes allows the system to perform automatic association without ambiguity. If the protocol is not followed, the "director" (Django) is unable to correctly map the 3D asset to the corresponding record in the repository, breaking the link between the visual object and the scientific data. This rigour ensures that the portal remains scalable. When the archive follows the standard, the system can process hundreds of models while guaranteeing that the texture of an amphora is never erroneously associated with another artefact. The folder named with the object code thus becomes the "primary key" that associates the visual component with the descriptive one.

Finally, the issue of the spatial consistency of annotations was addressed. Since the portal allows data to be "anchored" to specific points on the model, it is essential that the coordinates remain consistent even when the model is scaled or rotated within the viewer.

The system saves coordinates relative to the original geometry of the model, ensuring that the annotation "follows" the morphological detail of the artefact under all display conditions, in compliance with W3C Web Annotation standards. The resolution of these technical issues is not merely of informatic significance, but represents the construction of a certified environment in which the rigour of the upload pipeline guarantees the reliability of the portal.

The architecture of 3D V.I.S.O.R. was designed to move beyond the static model of traditional databases. The choice of technology stack aims to ensure maximum data integrity over time while simultaneously delivering the dynamic user experience required for international collaboration. Django was selected for its stability and for its authentication and database management system. The extension via DRF made it possible to expose robust and documented APIs, transforming complex archaeological metadata (relating to chronologies, materials, and provenances) into standardised JSON streams. This approach guarantees interoperability, allowing external systems to query the portal in a secure and structured manner. To elevate the portal to a collaborative platform, Django Channels was implemented. Unlike standard HTTP connections (which close after each request), the WebSockets enabled by Channels maintain a permanently open bi-directional

communication channel. This allows the server to "push" updates to users in real time: if a researcher adds an annotation to a 3D model, all other connected users will see the new pin instantaneously, without needing to reload the page. To orchestrate the passing of asynchronous messages between the various Django processes, Redis was adopted. This solution acts as a high-speed memory for live messages, ensuring that system notifications and collaborative activities are handled with near-zero latency, even under intensive workloads.

Figure 21 3D model visualisation screen in V.I.S.O.R.: in the upper left corner, the toolbar can be seen, providing access to the various tools available within the portal

The frontend is conceived as a virtual laboratory where data, once received from the backend, takes on a visible and manipulable form. React's component-based architecture allows complex interfaces (maps, catalogue records, and 3D viewers) to be managed in a modular fashion. Thanks to React, the transition from one artefact to another occurs seamlessly, updating only the necessary portions of the interface and drastically improving browsing speed. The visualisation of 3D artefacts is entrusted to R3F, the bridge that integrates Three.js into the React ecosystem. This allows 3D models (OBJ/MTL files) to be treated not as simple static files, but as interactive components with which the user can engage (click, measure, annotate). The use of specific utility libraries enables the rapid implementation of tools essential for analysis, such as advanced camera controls and loading systems that inform the user of the download progress of heavy assets. To support the study of artefacts through digital models, several post-processing algorithms have been integrated to improve the legibility of the object:

- **N8AO (Ambient Occlusion)**: implemented to generate realistic contact shadows in the cavities and surface irregularities of meshes. This effect is crucial as it highlights

surface details (such as cracks, inscriptions, or tool marks) that standard rendering would leave flat and difficult to read.

- **Bloom and ToneMapping:** used to correctly calibrate the luminous rendering of different materials (ceramics, metals, stones), ensuring that the perception of digital materials is as close as possible to the original under various virtual lighting conditions.

A decisive advantage arising from the use of React is the Single Page Application nature of the portal. This architecture plays a fundamental role in managing computational resources, especially in a scientific context characterised by heavy three-dimensional assets. Unlike traditional web applications, where every user interaction involves reloading the entire page and a new full request to the server, the SPA loads the application framework only once. Subsequently, React communicates with Django via lightweight API calls to retrieve only the strictly necessary data (metadata or annotation coordinates). The demanding task of rendering 3D models is delegated entirely to the client side (browser), drawing on the user's own computational capabilities. This means that the Django server does not need to generate images or complex visualisations, but simply serves static files, leaving the frontend to compose the interactive scene.

Since the visualisation of models is managed within a single application lifecycle, the user can move from the technical record to live annotations or 3D manipulation without any interruption. This avoids overloading the backend with redundant requests and ensures that the browser memory keeps already-loaded 3D resources active, making scientific exploration fast, responsive, and free from downtime.

3.4. Annotation system and interactive interface

3D V.I.S.O.R. also features a 3D object annotation tool. This module does not merely overlay information, but creates a link between the annotation and the morphology of the artefact. Unlike the prototype described in section 2.5, this tool provides the user with the ability to annotate a 3D object with text in natural language. To meet the potentially diverse needs of users, the system handles two modes of spatial selection:

- **Point Annotation (Raycasting):** through the use of raycasting algorithms on Three.js, the system calculates with millimetre precision the point of intersection between the user's cursor and the 3D mesh. This mode is ideal for identifying specific details, such as a single epigraphic character, a lacuna in the material, or a tool mark. The system saves the local coordinates (x , y , z), ensuring that the "pin" remains anchored to the geometry even when the model is rotated or zoomed.

- **Area Annotation (Selection Mask):** in addition to a single point, this tool allows broader areas of interest to be defined. This functionality is crucial for describing extended phenomena (e.g. an area of oxidation, a painted decoration, or an entire paragraph of an inscribed text). Area annotation makes it possible to delimit portions of the surface, associating the scholarly comment not with a point but with a defined region of the artefact.

One of the most innovative features of the workflow is its ability to process complex semantic input. The scholar can enter critical analyses in natural language, including reflections, bibliographic comparisons, or autoptic descriptions. Through a backend processing engine, the discursive text is processed to extract structured categories. The system is able to receive the analysis and organise it according to the parameters of the data model (e.g. distinguishing between function, material description, or transmission context). This step transforms a simple comment into an enriched text presenting searchable metadata in accordance with FAIR principles. Annotations can be linked to controlled vocabularies and external thesauri, allowing concepts to be mapped directly onto the digital replica of the object.

After entering the comment, the system saves not only the content and coordinates, but also the author's metadata, the timestamp, and the reference system used. When an annotation is saved, it can be broadcast via WebSocket to all connected researchers. This means that an international team can collaborate simultaneously on the same 3D model, seeing their colleagues' annotations appear in real time. The persistence system is designed to be compatible with the W3C Web Annotation model. This ensures that annotations produced within 3D V.I.S.O.R. are interoperable and can be exported or displayed in other scholarly contexts, in compliance with the data lifecycle prescribed by the infrastructure.

The user interacts with annotations through a highly refined React interface:

- by hovering the mouse over the "pins" or annotated areas, the 3D model responds visually, highlighting the point of interest.
- clicking on the annotation opens information panels that present the structured analysis in a readable format, incorporating supplementary images or links to external resources.

In summary, the annotation system elevates the portal from a simple viewer to a knowledge production platform, where 3D spatial interaction and the structuring of discursive text converge to offer a holistic view of the reproduced artefact.

Figure 22 Example of area selection for annotation: the image shows a simple AI that recognises when the shape is about to be closed. The image illustrates how, thanks to the robust structural architecture (DRF for the backend and React for the frontend), it is possible to display semantic annotations entered from different clients.

Figure 23 The image illustrates how, thanks to the robust structural architecture (DRF for the backend and React for the frontend), it is possible to display semantic annotations entered from different clients

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Figure 24 The image illustrates how artificial intelligence, if correctly trained, can return a structured analysis of a discursive text entered by the scholar

3.5. Multi-Device Accessibility and Responsive Design

The development of the prototype also involved optimising the portal for cross-device use. The objective is to ensure that the analysis tools are accessible not only from fixed workstations, but also from mobile devices (tablets and smartphones), supporting research directly in the field or while on the move.

The 3D viewer, based on the React ecosystem, was designed to adapt dynamically to different screen resolutions:

- the adaptive interface uses Material UI (MUI) flexible grids, side metadata panels, and annotation forms to automatically reposition the model view on smaller screens.
- the navigation controls were configured to recognise natural gestures (pinch-to-zoom, touch rotation), enabling smooth inspection of the artefact without the use of a mouse or keyboard.

In view of the computational requirements for visualising complex models, specific technical solutions were adopted:

- **Asset Scaling:** the frontend is able to request optimised versions of textures via Django's logic, reducing data consumption and the RAM load on the mobile device.
- **SPA Efficiency:** the Single Page Application (React) architecture minimises data transfers, loading only the essential information packages. This allows the researcher to consult complex artefact records even over a mobile network, while maintaining a responsive user experience.

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Portability transforms the portal into an operational support tool. The ability to access the Django proxy and display repository data directly in front of the physical artefact facilitates verification and cataloguing processes.

The responsive nature of the annotation module allows brief notes or preliminary "pins" to be entered via tablet during survey phases, which can then be elaborated in the office thanks to the real-time persistence guaranteed by the backend.

Figure 25 V.I.S.O.R. features a responsive interface that adapts to the viewport of the device on which it is displayed

The set of solutions adopted defines 3D VISOR as a mature digital ecosystem. The project is therefore not conceived merely as an archive, but as a dynamic infrastructure capable of supporting the researcher in their studies, while guaranteeing the integrity, traceability, and valorisation of material — and potentially epigraphic — data.

4. Conclusions

The set of tools designed by WP10 and the implementation of the related prototypes outlines guidelines for the possible construction of a system capable of integrating heterogeneous archaeological and epigraphic data and of developing tools for visualisation, metadata description, and annotation. Although deliverable D10.4 has demonstrated how it is possible to design and test a digital ecosystem for the processing, publication, and annotation of ancient religious resources — one capable of combining scientific rigour, interoperability, and technological sustainability — many uncertainties remain, connected to the lack of more thorough testing on integration. The highly circumscribed case studies, and the absence at the international level of standards for ancient religious studies (objects and texts) — generally encompassed within the broader sphere of the study of the past — have not allowed other avenues for integration to be explored. Nevertheless, the proposed methodology appears, at this stage, to be the only scalable and genuinely cross-domain solution.

The report presents an articulated set of methodologies and prototypes developed in the context of WP10, illustrating a multi-layered approach to the digitisation of ancient religious resources. Through concrete case studies, the work has highlighted the intrinsic complexity of religious data, which requires flexible and multi-level descriptive models, and has underscored how the integration of established standards (TEI, Dublin Core, IIF, Web Annotation, OAI-PMH, RDF) can promote the circulation and reuse of information in compliance with FAIR principles and Open Science — also thanks to the use of advanced technologies connected to AI (HTR, NER, etc.) or to interactive 3D visualisation.

Deliverable D10.4 presents a technologically robust prototype that integrates 3D visualisation, semantic annotation, and modern web architecture to support research on ancient religious heritage. The report highlights the current limitations of generalist metadata schemas and the need to accept compromises between semantic richness (TEI) and interoperability (DC), especially when the aim is to support collaborative research practices and natural language annotations. In this perspective, ReTINA does not present itself as a definitive solution, but as a methodological and exploratory model — replicable and adaptable to other cultural contexts — that contributes to strengthening the RESILIENCE infrastructure by providing tools and guidelines for a more articulated and shared representation of ancient religious heritage.

Significant challenges certainly remain, linked to the loss of information in semantic mapping processes, the sustainability of solutions based on third-party tools, and the effective interoperability in the context of highly heterogeneous and specialised resources. The very choice of privileging natural language annotations, while on the one hand facilitating adoption by scholars, on the other risks limiting the capacity for semantic

querying and automatic integration. To transform the prototypes into a stable and scalable ecosystem, it will be necessary to address these methodological tensions and assess the real impact of the tools on interdisciplinary research practice. The absence of quantitative metrics, usability testing with the scholarly community, and broader experiments in semantic extraction from natural language may raise questions about the system's ability to respond to the various needs of researchers.

In conclusion, D10.4 describes a significant advance in the creation of a digital ecosystem for religious studies, succeeding in integrating different standards into a single functional interface. Although automation via HTR and metadata mapping still present margins of error and forced simplifications, the approach based on Linked Open Data and URI enrichment lays the foundations for an interoperable research infrastructure. The future challenge will also reside in overcoming institutional barriers to data access and in refining machine learning models for less widely spoken ancient languages. In this regard, it is desirable that a roadmap be defined for effective integration with external resources — a fundamental element for realising the vision of an interoperable ecosystem for religious studies. Without these further developments, the prototype risks remain a promising but isolated technological demonstration, rather than becoming a transformative tool for religious research.

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